

Research Article

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POTASSIUM ALUM FACE SCRUB

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Abstract:

Potassium alum, known for its astringent and antibacterial properties, has been utilized in various cosmetic applications. This study focuses on the development of a potassium alum-based facial scrub and assesses its potential effectiveness in facilitating skin exfoliation and improving overall dermal texture. The formulated scrub combines natural exfoliants and moisturizing agents to enhance skin health. The study evaluates parameters such as Color, Fragrance, Texture, Consistency, pH Measurement, Viscosity, Spreadability, Physical Stability, Patch Test, Efficacy Testing. Given its natural origin, affordability, and proven benefits, potassium alum-based face packs could serve as a sustainable and effective alternative to chemical-laden commercial products.[1]

Keywords: Potassium alum, face scrub, exfoliation, skin care, formulation, evaluation.

Introduction:

The skin is the largest organ in the human body, envelops the entire exterior surface and protects it from a variety of factors. On a surface of 1.5-2m², the skin functions as the body's primary defense mechanism against pathogens, ultraviolet rays, chemicals, and physical trauma. It should play an important role in regulating control of body temperature and environmental release.

Human skin is generally classified into five primary types based on its physiological characteristics: normal, dry, oily, combination (exhibiting both oily and dry regions), and sensitive.[2]

Drug Information:

Potassium alum ($KAl(SO_4)_2 \cdot 12H_2O$) is a naturally occurring sulfate mineral widely recognized for its astringent, antimicrobial, and hemostatic properties. Historically, it has been used in water purification, medicine, and traditional skincare remedies. In dermatology and cosmetic science, potassium alum is used in face scrubs and skincare formulations due to its ability to tighten pores, reduce oil secretion, and combat bacterial growth. Face scrubs containing potassium alum leverage its exfoliating and antibacterial properties to promote clearer, healthier skin. With the growing preference for natural and sustainable skincare solutions, potassium alum-based formulations are gaining attention as effective alternatives to synthetic skincare chemicals.[3,4]

Potassium Alum as an Active Ingredient:

Potassium alum has long been used in skincare for its **astringent, antibacterial, and antiseptic properties**. It works by tightening the skin, reducing oil secretion, and preventing bacterial growth, "This makes it a particularly suitable option for individuals with acne-prone and oily skin types, due to its potential to regulate sebum production and minimize pore congestion. In a face scrub, It enhances **exfoliation, pore-tightening, and oil control**, leading to a **refreshed and clearer complexion**. [4]

Fig no. 1: Potassium Alum

Benefits of Potassium Alum Face Scrub:

1. **Astringent Properties:** Potassium alum aids in pore constriction and the regulation of excess sebum, beneficial for individuals oily and acne-prone skin.
2. **Antibacterial Action:** It should inhibits the growth of bacteria, reducing the occurrence of acne and other skin infections.

3. **Exfoliation:** Combined with exfoliating agents, potassium alum aids in the removal of dead skin cells, promoting a smoother and healthier complexion.
4. **Skin Soothing:** Due to its inherent anti-inflammatory properties, potassium alum can help soothe irritated skin and diminish redness, contributing to an overall calming effect.
5. **Odor Control:** Due to its ability to neutralize bacteria responsible for body odor, potassium alum contributes to fresh and clean skin.
6. **Safe for Sensitive Skin:** Being a natural mineral, it generally well-tolerated by most skin types when formulated appropriately.[5]

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

A. Ingredients

1. Potassium Alum:

1. **Synonym:** Potash Alum, Aluminum Potassium Sulfate
2. **Biological Source:** Naturally occurring mineral (Alum group) obtained from bauxite and alunite
3. **Description:**
 - **Colour:** White or colorless crystalline solid
 - **Odour:** Odorless
 - **Taste:** Astringent, slightly sweetish
4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**
 - Potassium aluminum sulfate ($KAl(SO_4)_2 \cdot 12H_2O$)
5. **Uses:**
 - Acts as an astringent, antiseptic, and antimicrobial agent
 - Helps in tightening pores and controlling oil secretion
 - Reduces acne and prevents bacterial growth

2. Multani Mitti:

1. **Synonym:** Fuller's Earth, Bentonite Clay
2. **Biological Source:** Naturally occurring clay derived from decomposed volcanic ash
3. **Description:**
 - **Colour:** Light brown to beige
 - **Odour:** Earthy
 - **Taste:** Tasteless
4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**
 - Hydrated aluminum silicates, magnesium, calcium, iron oxides

5. Uses:

- Absorbs excess oil and dirt from the skin
- Acts as a natural cleanser and detoxifier
- Improves skin tone and texture

3. Aloe Vera Gel:

1. **Synonym:** Aloe barbadensis gel

2. **Biological Source:** Extracted from the **Aloe barbadensis miller** plant leaves

3. **Description:**

- **Colour:** Transparent to light green
- **Odour:** Mild, fresh odor
- **Taste:** Bitter

4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**

- Polysaccharides (Acemannan), Vitamins (A, C, E), Enzymes, Amino acids

5. **Uses:**

- Hydrates and soothes the skin
- Has anti-inflammatory and wound-healing properties
- Acts as a natural moisturizer and anti-aging agent

4. Rose Water:

1. **Synonym:** Gulab Jal

2. **Biological Source:** Extracted from fresh petals of **Rosa damascena**

3. **Description:**

- **Colour:** Colorless to pale pink liquid
- **Odour:** Floral, characteristic rose scent
- **Taste:** Slightly sweet, floral

4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**

- Essential oils, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic compounds

5. **Uses:**

- Acts as a natural toner and skin refresher
- Has anti-inflammatory and hydrating properties
- Soothes irritated skin and balances pH

5. Glycerine:

1. **Synonym:** Glycerol
2. **Biological Source:** Derived from plant oils (coconut, palm) or animal fats
3. **Description:**

- **Colour:** Colorless, viscous liquid
- **Odour:** Odorless
- **Taste:** Sweet

4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**

- Glycerol (C₃H₈O₃), hydroxyl groups

5. **Uses:**

- Acts as a humectant, retaining moisture in the skin
- Softens and hydrates the skin
- Improves the spreadability of formulations

6. Vitamin E oil:

1. **Synonym:** Tocopherol
2. **Biological Source:** Derived from plant oils (sunflower, wheat germ, almond)
3. **Description:**

- **Colour:** Yellow to brownish viscous liquid
- **Odour:** Mild, characteristic odor
- **Taste:** Slightly oily taste

4. **Chief Chemical Constituents:**

- Tocopherols and tocotrienols (lipophilic antioxidants)

5. **Uses:**

- Acts as a powerful antioxidant, protecting skin from oxidative stress
- Promotes skin healing and hydration
- Prevents premature aging and enhances skin elasticity

7. Masoor Dal (Red Lentil Powder):

1. **Synonym:** Lens culinaris powder
2. **Biological Source:** Ground seeds of **Lens culinaris**
3. **Description:**

- **Colour:** Light orange to reddish-brown powder
- **Odour:** Mild nutty scent
- **Taste:** Slightly earthy, nutty

4. Chief Chemical Constituents:

- Proteins, carbohydrates, fiber, vitamins (B-complex)

5. Uses:

- a natural exfoliant, removing dead skin cells
- Brightens skin complexion or reduces pigmentation
- Helps in controlling excess oil and acne

Fig: Potassium alum powder

Fig: Multani mitti powder

Fig: aloe vera gel

Fig: Rose water

Fig: Glycerin

Fig: Vit E gel

Fig: Masoor

Fig no. 10: Ingredients Images

Equipments:

Sr no.	Apparatus or Equipments
1.	Weight machine
2.	Mortar and pestle
3.	Glass rod stirrer
4.	Beakers
5.	pH meter
6.	Sieve
7.	Magnetic stirrer machine
8.	Oswalt Viscometer

Table No. 1 List of equipments

METHODOLOGY:

Method or procedure:

In order to formulate the face scrub these are the following steps: All the ingredients readily prepared were brought from the market.

Procedure for the production of facial scrubbing. Measure the necessary ingredients with a digital balance. Next[6]

Pre-Treatment of Ingredients

1. Grinding & Sieving:

Potassium Alum is ground into particle size, grind to a fine powder using a **mortar or pestle**.

Masoor Dal are finely milled and passed through a **sieve (mesh size 80–100)** to obtain a fine exfoliating powder. **Multani Mitti** is sieved to remove lumps and ensure smooth blending.

2. Preparation of Liquid Phase:

Aloe Vera Gel, Rose Water, Glycerine, and Vitamin E Oil are blended using a **magnetic stirrer** at 300 rpm for 5 minutes. The mixture is allowed to stand for 10 minutes to remove air bubbles.

❖ Preparation of the Face Scrub

Step 1: Dry Phase Mixing

Potassium Alum, Multani Mitti, and Masoor Dal are mixed in a **sterile glass beaker** and stirred using a **glass rod** for 2–3 minutes until a uniform powder blend is obtained.

Step 2: Liquid Phase Incorporation

The **liquid phase (Aloe vera gel, Rose water, Glycerine, and Vitamin E Oil)** are **slowly added** to the dry mixture while **continuously stirring** to prevent clumping.

The mixing is performed using **mortar and pestle** for **10 minutes** to ensure **homogeneity**.

Step 3: Final Blending

The scrub mixture is **manually** for 5 minutes to obtain a **smooth, non-sticky, and uniform paste**.

The formulation is allowed to rest for **30 minutes** to stabilize and enhance binding between ingredients.

❖ Storage & Packaging

The final scrub is stored in **sterilized container** and labeled with batch numbers.

Samples are stored in different **temperatures (4° C, 25° C, and 40° C)** to study stability.[7]

Fig no. 3: Potassium Alum fine powder Powder

Fig no. 4: Multani Mitti

Fig no. 5: Masoor Dal passed through a sieve

Fig no. 6: Dry Phase Mixing

Fig no. 7: Liquid Phase Incorporation

Fig no. 8: Final Blending

Fig no. 9: Final scrub

Fig no. 10: Face scrub

Formulation table:

Sr no.	Ingredients (g/ml)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Potassium Alum	1.5g	1.8g	2.2g	2.0g	1.9g
2.	Multani Mitti	2.0g	2.7g	2.3g	2.6g	2.4g

3.	Aloe Vera Gel	2.2 ml	2.3ml	2.7ml	2.4ml	2.6ml
4.	Glycerine	0.5 ml	0.8ml	0.6ml	0.9ml	0.7ml
5.	Vitamin E	1.0 ml	2.0ml	1.5ml	1.7ml	1.6ml
6.	Masoor Dal (Red Lentil Powder)	0.4 g	0.4g	0.7g	0.4g	0.6g
7.	Rose Water	Q. s	Q. s	Q. s	Q. s	Q. s
8.	Total (g/ml)	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0

Table no. 2: Formulation table

Fig no. 11: Image of prepared formulations

Instructions of use?

1. Cleanse Your Face
2. Apply the Face Scrub
3. Massage Gently.
4. Rinse with Lukewarm Water
5. Use 2-3 Times a Week

Evaluation tests:

The formulated facial exfoliant was evaluated using a comprehensive set of parameters, including organoleptic properties, pH, skin irritability, washability, grittiness, extrudability, foamability, and spreadability. All assessed characteristics complied with the established standards. The final product demonstrated effective exfoliating and cleansing properties, contributing to improved skin clarity and radiance.

The formulated face scrub was systematically evaluated based on a range of physicochemical and sensory parameters, including color, fragrance, texture, consistency, washability, pH, viscosity, spreadability, physical stability, homogeneity, and dermatological safety through a patch test. The formulation exhibited favorable application properties, with ease of application and removal, and demonstrated compatibility with various skin types.[8]

1. **Organoleptic Property:** Appearance or colour was observed in visual inspection. The smell was examined by the smell.

2. **Washability:** The skin is scrubbed with a small bit of face scrub and then rinsed with water. Washing was easy.[9]

3. **pH:** pH measurement is essential to determine the acidity or alkalinity of topical formulations and to ensure compatibility with the skin's natural pH. For this study, pH of formulated face scrub are determined using a calibrated digital pH meter. The formulation sample was submerged in the electrode, or pH readings were recorded at a controlled temperature to ensure accuracy. This evaluation helps confirm that the scrub falls within the acceptable pH range for dermal application.

Fig no. 12: PH

4. **Viscosity:** Viscosity of scrub are measured by using an oswald visual meter. The device measures viscosity by observing the time when a well-known amount of liquid passes through the capillary tube.

Fig no. 13: Viscosity

5. **Spreadability:** Spreadability testing evaluates the ease with which the scrub spreads on the skin surface. In this test, approximately 1 g of the formulated scrub was placed between two glass slides, or a standard weight of 100 g was applied to the upper slide to simulate pressure. After 60 seconds, the extent of spread and the ease of film displacement were measured to assess the formulation's spreadability performance.[10]

The result are obtained by applying a specific formula,

$$S = m \times l \times t$$

Where, S= Spreadability

m=Weight placed on slide
 l= Length of glass slide
 t= Time taken in sec

Fig no. 14: Spreadability

6. **Stability study:** The formulation are stored under various temperature conditions for the period of 60 days and periodically evaluated for parameters including color, odor, pH, and consistency. These evaluations were carried out to track any modifications to the formulation's chemical and physical stability over time.
7. **Patch Test:** A patch test is done to check if a product causes any skin allergies. The small amount of product is applied a small area of the skin in a diluted form, and the skin reaction is observed for **2-3 days**.The **Scrub** are cosmetic product, we tested on people with different skin tones, including **faired, dark, moderately dark, medium fair, or medium skin tones**. This helps ensure the product is safe for everyone.
8. **Homogeneity:** Homogeneity of the formulated face scrub was assessed through visual inspection and tactile evaluation to ensure uniform distribution of components throughout the product.[11]

9. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Sr no.	Parameters	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
1.	Color	Yellowish-brown	Yellowish-brown	Yellowish-brown	Yellowish-brown	Yellowish-brown
2.	Fragrance	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic	Characteristic
3.	Texture	Fine or good	Fine or good	Fine or good	Fine or good	Fine or good
4.	Consistency	Good	Good	Good	Good	Good
5.	Washability	Easy washable	Easy washable	Easy washable	Easy washable	Easy washable
6.	pH Measurement	5.76	5.13	5.2	5.04	5.05
6.	Viscosity	2.18 cPa	2.13 cPa	2.0 cPa	2.15 cPa	2.1 cPa
7.	Spreadability	Easy Spreadable	Easy Spreadable	Easy Spreadable	Easy Spreadable	Easy Spreadable
8.	Patch Test	Non-irritant, Nott Allergic Reaction	Non-irritant, Not Allergic Reaction			

Table no. 3: Evaluation tests results

Formulation F1, F2, F3, F4 and F5 underwent testing for evaluation parameters including Color, Fragrance, Texture, Consistency, Washability, pH Measurement, Viscosity, Spreadability, Physical Stability, Patch Test, Homogeneity.[12]

1. Organoleptic Property:

- a. **Colour** – Visual inspection reveals that the face scrub has a yellowish brown hue.
- b. **Fragrance** – Odour are found Characteristic.
- c. **Texture** - Fine and good
- b. **Consistency**- Check grittiness, softness, Consistency are found to be smooth with visual observation

2. Viscosity: The **Ostwald viscometer** was used to measure the viscosity of the scrub formulations, and the findings were noted.

Formula for Viscosity Calculation:

$$\eta_1 = \eta_0 \times (t_0/t_1) \times (\rho_0/\rho_1)$$

where,

η_1 = Viscosity of the test sample (face scrub) in centipoise (cP)

η_0 = Viscosity of water at 25°C (1 cP or 0.001 Pa·s)

t_1 = Flow time of the test sample (in seconds)

t_0 = Flow time of water (in seconds)

ρ_1 = Density of the test sample (g/mL)

ρ_0 = Density of water (1 g/mL at 25°C)

Table no. 4: Viscosity of formulations

Sr.no	Formulations	Viscosity (cPa)
a)	F1	2.18 cPa
b)	F2	2.13 cPa
c)	F3	2.0 cPa
d)	F4	2.15 cPa
e)	F5	2.1 cPa

3. pH:

Using a calibrated digital pH meter, the pH of the scrub formulations was assessed, and readings were noted.

Table no. 5: pH of formulations

Sr.no	Formulations	pH
a)	F1	5.76
b)	F2	5.13
c)	F3	5.2
d)	F4	5.04
e)	F5	5.05

4. Spreadability:

At room temperature, the scrub formulations' spreadability was assessed. Below are the spreadability data for each scrub formulation.[13]

Table no.6: Spreadability of formulations

Sr.no	Formulations	Spreadability (g.cm/sec)
a)	F1	4.5
b)	F2	4.8
c)	F3	5.5
d)	F4	5.1
e)	F5	6

DISCUSSION:

In the study, naturally potassium-alum-Alum-Scrub was prescribed or evaluated. Scrub contains potassium-aluminum powder, murtani-mitti, arobar-gel, glycerin, vitamin E, masordal, and rose water. It has peeling properties, soothes dry skin, removes dirt particles, and decreases dark spots. F1 through F5 were developed for several evaluation factors such as color, aroma, texture, consistency, washable, pH measurement, viscosity, diffusion, physical stability, patch test, and uniformity. The product colour was a yellowish-brown color with a distinctive smell. The product's pH value was 5, and the product consistency are satisfactory with small, coarse grain particles. Formulation F1 was highly effective compared to other five formulations. F5 exhibited viscosity of 2.1 cps and it easily diffused with a diffusivity of 5g.cm/sec. Furthermore, peeling was easy to wash with regular water. Therefore, the developed wording can used as an effective exfoliation to an achieve to healthy and bright skin.[14]

CONCLUSION:

In the study, goal are should be develop effective and stable facial scrubbing with natural ingredients. Five formulations were prepared or compared to various parameters such as color, odor, pH, distribution, patch test, and washing. The viscosity and pH values of F1 are within the expected region, and the distributed values indicate that the product is more likely to become popular. F1 showed good consistency without oil separation, no uniform particle aggregation and it are easily washed with normal water.

Therefore, formulation F1 show the desired results and was most effective compared to the other four formulations. i.e F2, F3, F4, F5. Finally, potassium aluminum is well formulated as potassium-around-facial exfoliation with other natural ingredients. Based on the results of the evaluation, you can effectively use the formulated potassium-Alum-Face-scrub are improve quality of your skin and achieve beautiful skin [15,16]

References

- [1] D. M. S. Mansi E. Jadhav, "FORMULATION & EVALUATION OF ALUM TONER," *ournal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, Vols. Volume 11, , no. Issue 12 , p. 11, 2024.
- [2] T. A. T. Rutuja Prashant Nangare¹, "Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Facial Scrub," *International Journal of Research Publication and Reviews* , no. 2582-7421, p. 10, 2022.
- [3] A. U. G. ., A. K. D. M. T. M. A. P. Sachin Bhagwat Aglawe*, "Preparation and evaluation of polyherbal facial scrub," *Journal of Drug Delivery and Therapeutics*, no. 2250-1177 , p. 3, 2019.
- [4] C. T. G. Shruti Satish Garad^{1*}, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF MULTIUSE POLYHERBAL," *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* , Vols. Volume 13,, no. Issue 13, 712-725., p. 14, 2024.
- [5] 1. M. C. 2. P. D. G. *Dr. Shweta P. Ghode, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FACIAL SCRUB CONTAINING SUNFLOWER SEEDS AND OTHER NATURAL INGREDIENTS," *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vols. Volume 8 , , no. 9, 1772-1781. , p. 10, 2019.
- [6] 2. N. K. 3. A. N. 1*Khairani Fitri, "FORMULATION AND PHYSICAL STABILITY TESTING OF CREAM SCRUB PREPARATIONS FROM ETHANOL EXTRACT OF Nelumbo nucifera GAERTN FLOWER AND LEAF," *Jurnal Biotik*, vol. Vol. 12, no. April 2024, p. 15, 2024.
- [7] K. J. a. D. S. T. Fariah Rizwani, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL FACE-SCRUB," *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*, Vols. Volume 12, , no. 9, 1570-1577. , p. 8, 2023.
- [8] H. P. B. N. Harshitha R¹, "Formulation and Evaluation of Natural Rice Flour Face Scrub," *International Journal of Research and Review*, vol. Volume 11, no. 12; December 2024, p. 10, 2024 .
- [9] P. Z. Y. D. P. U. Kiran Pandit Paradkar^{*1}, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF FACIAL SCRUB FROM CHICKOO," *International Research Journal of Modernization in Engineering Technology and Science* , no. 2582-5208, p. 12, 2024.
- [10] N. D. Kiran Yadav¹, "Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub by Using Tamarind Peel Powder," *International Journal of Scientific Research for Global Innovation*, vol. Volume 01, no. 02 (July) 2024, p. 11, 2024.
- [11] M. S. C. M. Miss. Chetana S. Waghmare¹, "Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub that Exfoliates Skin with Coffee," *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. Volume 6, no. 3, May-June 2024, p. 11, 2024 .
- [12] P. K. S. D. K. P. Mounika¹, "Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Face Scrub Using Exfoliating Agents," *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, vol. Volume 5, no. 5, September-October 2023, p. 8, 2023.
- [13] M. T. R. Paigude, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF ALUM TONER SPRAY FOR ANTI-ACNE," *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF CREATIVE RESEARCH THOUGHTS*, Vols. Volume 11,, no. Issue 5 May 2023 , p. 13, 2023.
- [14] S. T. Polly Gupta², "Formulation And Evaluation Of Face Scrub In Modern Pharmaceutics," *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF* , vol. Vol 2, no. 3, 579-588, p. 12, 2024.
- [15] B. P. D. Pratiksha Baravkar*, "FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLY HERBAL FACIAL SCRUB," *World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research* , vol. Volume 13, no. 10, 944-961., p. 18, 2024.
- [16] S. T. S. M. a. D. M. Sushil Kumar Pal *, "Formulation and evaluation of herbal face scrub," *International Journal of Scientific Research Updates*, no. 01 October 2024, p. 12, 2024.